

Supplementary material for the article:
**Tracing evolutionary trajectories in the presence of
gene flow in South American temperate lizards
(Squamata: *Liolaemus kingii* group)**

Supplementary text

Text S1: Taxonomic history of the *Liolaemus kingii* group

The taxonomy of this group of lizards began with the description of *Liolaemus kingii* by Bell (1843) (as *Proctotretus kingii*), based on comparisons with *L. fitzingerii* Duméril & Bibron 1837 (see also Cei 1980). Both species were distinguished by the morphology of cephalic and dorsal scales and the squamation pattern on the thighs. This author designated “Puerto Deseado, Patagonia” (Santa Cruz, Argentina) as its type locality (Bell 1843; see also Duméril 1852). Gray (1845) subsequently allocated this and other species assigned to *Proctotretus* in the genus *Liolaemus* Wiegmann 1834 (*Leioælmus*). The genus *Rhytidodeira* was proposed by Girard (1857) to include *P. kingii* Bell 1843 among other species. However, Baird (1858) considered *Rhytidodeira* as a subgenus of *Proctotretus* Duméril & Bibron 1837. Later, Boulenger (1885) grouped all these entities within the genus *Liolaemus* (see also Burmeister 1888; Koslowsky 1896, 1898; Werner 1896; Stejneger 1909; Barbour 1921; Burt and Burt 1930, 1931, 1933; Donoso-Barros and Codoceo 1962; Peters and Donoso-Barros 1970; Donoso-Barros 1970; Gallardo 1971).

Donoso-Barros and Cei (1971) described *Liolaemus archeforus*, an endemic species of the basaltic plateau of Lago Buenos Aires (NW Santa Cruz province, Argentina). These authors established morphological affinities with *L. kingii*, although with differences in the patterns of dorsal bands, number of scales around the midbody, and shape of the dorsal scales (Donoso-Barros and Cei 1971). Donoso-Barros (1973) described *L. sarmientoi* based on material previously ascribed to a population of *L. dorbignyi* Koslowsky 1898, and designed its type locality in Monte Aymond, in the Argentina–Chile border. This author also proposed the name “*kingii* group” to include *L. archeforus*, *L. kingii*, and *L. sarmientoi*. The . Using morphological and serological attributes, Cei (1975) validated the specific status of *L. kingii* and *L. archeforus* (*L. archeforus archeforus*), considered *L. sarmientoi* as a subspecies of *L. archeforus* (*L. archeforus sarmientoi*), and proposed that these three entities form a natural group, the “*kingii* group.” He also suggested that *L. archeforus archeforus* represent an ancestral lineage derived from *L. kingii*, whose characteristics might have evolved in geographical isolation during the Pleistocene glacial expansion (Cei 1975). Cei (1979) grouped all these species in the “*L. kingii-archeforus* complex,” which was characterized by the following synapomorphies: 1) absence of a femoral patch, 2) “moderately high” number of slightly keeled scales around the body (58–84), 3) high number of precloacal pores (6–10), 4) short legs and tail (slightly longer than the body), 5) variegated ventral coloration and absence of dark coloration in the nuchal

region, and 6) dark dorsal background with a series of yellowish or whitish transverse bars. The author also highlighted that the diversity of this complex is conserved in comparison to other complexes that have apparently undergone recent speciation (after the Pleistocene; Cei 1979). Cei and Scolaro (1981) described *L. somuncurae* as *L. kingii somuncurae*, an isolated subspecies in the Somuncurá plateau (southern Río Negro province, Argentina)¹. These authors argued that this population probably diverged from the nominal form during a dry Pleistocene glacial phase, promoting the expansion of individuals from cooler steppe environments northward (Cei and Scolaro 1981). A year later, *L. gallardoi* was described (as *L. archeforus gallardoi*), and its type locality was established in Águila-Asador plateau (W Santa Cruz, Argentina; Cei and Scolaro 1982). These authors conducted a thorough review of the characters defining the “*kingii-archeforus* complex,” justifying the separation of the morphological groups “*kingii*” (*L. somuncurae* and *L. kingii*) and “*archeforus*” (*L. archeforus archeforus*, *L. archeforus gallardoi*, and *L. archeforus sarmientoi*). The former was characterized by a high number of small scales around the body and the latter by a lower number of larger scales (Cei and Scolaro 1982). In this work they also hypothesized evolutionary relationships between these lineages. It was proposed that the *kingii* group is a primitive lineage of the *kingii-archeforus* complex, while the *archeforus* group might represent a derived lineage for possessing an “apparently late periglacial specialized habitat appearance” (Cei and Scolaro 1982). In 1983, Cei and Scolaro described *L. baguali* (as *L. kingii baguali*), establishing Sierra del Bagual (SW Santa Cruz, Argentina) as its type locality (Cei and Scolaro 1983). In this work, the taxonomic separation of the *archeforus* and *kingii* groups was reinforced, and their geographic distributions were restricted: the *archeforus* group is predominantly found in the volcanic reliefs along the Patagonian mountain ranges, while the *kingii* group exhibits a more expansive distribution, spanning from the coastal region of Santa Cruz in the east to the sub-Andean distribution limits of the *archeforus* group in the west (Cei and Scolaro 1983).

Laurent (1983) carried out a taxonomic review of the genus *Liolaemus* based on morphometric features and defined two main groups: *Liolaemus sensu stricto* or Chilean group and *Eulaemus* Girard 1857 or Argentinean group (see also Laurent 1984; Pereyra et al. 1992). He also suggested that the “*kingii* group” (= *kingii* + *archeforus* groups) is related to the common ancestor of the genus, from which three lineages emerged: a group composed of *L. magellanicus* and *L. lineomaculatus* (“Fueguian lineage”), the Chilean group, and the Argentine group (Laurent 1983). Two years later, this author reinforced the separation of the main groups of *Liolaemus* through discriminant analyses, while also proposing a series of systematic changes (Laurent 1985). One of the changes involved the inclusion of *L. ruizleali* Donoso-Barros and Cei, 1971 within the “*kingii* group” (= *kingii* group + *L. ruizleali*) based on similarities in the width of the mental scale (Laurent 1985). He also resurrected the genus *Rhytidodeira* Girard 1857 to include these “primitive” species related to the Argentinean group (*Eulaemus*), designating *L. kingii* as the type species. Moreover, he proposed phenetic relationships among the main groups included in *Liolaemus*². Alternately, he suggested that the “*kingii* group” might belong to the Vilcunia–*L. magellanicus** branch, as a basal derivation or “ancestral stock” (Laurent 1985).

In a monograph on reptiles from central and southern Argentina, Cei (1986) included the “*kingii*”

¹See Cei (1985) for a correction of voucher numbers of the type series.

²Regarding these proposals, two observations should be noted: 1) Pincheira-Donoso and Núñez (2005) noted that the distant *L. bibronii* had been designated as the type species of *Rhytidodeira* by Donoso-Barros (1970) and invalidated the name *Rhytidodeira* for the *kingii* group + *L. ruizleali*; 2) Cei and Scolaro (1987) resolved that the holotype and some of the paratypes of *L. ruizleali* were in fact *L. rothi* specimens and hence the former should be removed from the “*kingii* group,” while the rest of the paratypes were assigned to *L. kingii somuncurae* (see also Cei (1990)).

groups (*L. kingii kingii*, *L. kingii somuncurae*, and *L. kingii baguali*) and “*archeforus*” groups (*L. archeforus archeforus*, *L. archeforus sarmientoi*, and *L. archeforus gallardoi*) in the genus *Liolaemus*. Laurent (1995), on the other hand, suggested that *Rhytidodeira* should be considered a subgenus of *Liolaemus*, a proposal not taken into account by Etheridge (1995), who grouped the species assigned to *Rhytidodeira*, *Vilcunia*, and *Eulaemus* within the genus *Liolaemus* (*sensu lato*). In the same publication, he recognized two large groups within the genus *Liolaemus*: the *nitidus* group (including the *lineomaculatus* and *chiliensis* groups = *L. sensu stricto*) and the *signifer* group. Due to a lack of diagnostic morphological attributes, *L. kingii* and *L. archeforus* could not be included in any of those groups (Etheridge 1995).

Cei and Scolaro (1996) described *L. zullyi* (name corrected to *L. zullyae* by Michels and Bauer 2004) and designed the Río Zeballos valley as its type locality (Jeinemeni River basin, NW Santa Cruz, Argentina). This species was included in the “*archeforus*” group. These authors noted that the high number of scales around the body in this species was similar to members of the “*kingii*” group. However, they justified its inclusion in the “*archeforus*” group due to its longer anterior limbs compared to members of the “*kingii*” group, markedly keeled dorsal scales, prevalence of red and orange scales in dorsolateral patterns, and ventral melanism. In this work, the authors also elevated the taxonomic rank of lineages included in the “*kingii*” and “*archeforus*” (subspecies) to full species because of their diagnosability and allopatric distribution, although the separation between the two groups was maintained (Cei and Scolaro 1996). A year later, a systematic review of the “*kingii*” and “*archeforus*” groups was published based on morphological attributes and a numerical approach (Scolaro and Cei 1997). Three new species were also described: *L. tristis* (“*kingii*” group) with the type locality in Lagunas Sin Fondo plateau (north–center Santa Cruz, Argentina), *L. tari*, and *L. escarchadosi* (“*archeforus*” group, although morphologically related to *L. sarmientoi*), with type localities in Viento plateau and Escarchados ridge, respectively (SW Santa Cruz, Argentina). In addition, these authors cited a personal communication of Etheridge where he proposed that “all the characteristics shared by the members of the ‘*kingii*’ and ‘*archeforus*’ groups are plesiomorphic” (Scolaro and Cei 1997).

The first statistical phylogenetic analysis involving species from the *Liolaemus kingii* group was conducted by Young-Downey (1998) based on molecular characters (allozymes) and a parsimony framework. This study confirmed the monophyly of the two major groups within *Liolaemus* (*L. sensu stricto* and *Eulaemus*). Additionally, Young-Downey (1998) identified a clade comprising *L. lineomaculatus*, *L. kingii*, *L. archeforus*, and *L. silvanae*, named the “Patagonian” group of *Eulaemus* (= *L. lineomaculatus* section). Subsequent studies supported these findings (Schulte et al. 2000; Morando 2004; Espinoza et al. 2004; Schulte and Moreno-Roark 2010; Breitman et al. 2011; Pyron et al. 2013; Olave et al. 2014; Esquerré et al. 2019a). Schulte et al. (2000) also employed a parsimony approach to analyze mitochondrial data and inferred a monophyletic group within *Eulaemus* comprising *L. lineomaculatus*, *L. somuncurae*, and *L. magellanicus*, distributed in the lowlands of southeastern Andes and referred to as the “*lineomaculatus* section”. Lobo (2001) published a morphological phylogeny of the *Eulaemus* subgenus, being this the only study not confirming the monophyly of the *lineomaculatus* section.

Liolaemus scolaro (*L. Donosolaemus scolaro*) was described by Pincheira-Donoso and Núñez (2005) within the “*archeforus* group,” with the type locality in Jeinemeni (Administrative Region XI, Chile). They proposed the subgenus *Donosolaemus* (= *Rhytidodeira sensu* Laurent, 1985) to include species assigned to the “*kingii*” and “*archeforus*” groups (*sensu* Scolaro and Cei (1997)), based on a unique combination of characters within *Liolaemus*. *Liolaemus archeforus* (*L. Donosolaemus archeforus*) was designated as the type species of this new subgenus (Pincheira-Donoso and

Núñez 2005). However, Lobo et al. (2010) invalidated this proposal because of a lack of synapomorphies and because it is nested within the subgenus *Eulaemus*, which would render the latter paraphyletic.

The following year, Scolaro and Cei (2006) described *Liolaemus uptoni*, a species related to *L. somuncurae* (the “*kingii*” group), with the type locality in Bajada del Buey (western Pampa de Sacanana, north-center Chubut, Argentina).

Breitman et al. (2011) published the first molecular phylogeny including all species included in the *L. lineomaculatus* section. They employed multilocus data, incorporating both nuclear and mitochondrial markers, and employed concatenation (parsimony and likelihood) and coalescent methods. Two key findings from this study were: 1) *L. somuncurae* and *L. uptoni* constituted a well-supported clade (the “*somuncurae*” group) separate from the clade formed by the rest of the species traditionally classified within the “*kingii*” and “*archeforus*” groups; 2) the reciprocal monophyly between the “*kingii*” and “*archeforus*” groups was not supported (also see Espinoza et al. (2004), Schulte and Moreno-Roark (2010), Pyron et al. (2013), Olave et al. (2014), and Esquerré et al. (2019b)), which led the authors to coin the term “*kingii* + *archeforus*” to denote the clade encompassing both species groups. The divergence between this clade and the “*somuncurae*” group was estimated at ~4.25 million years. In this study, five candidate species were also proposed for the whole group, one of which (*L. sp. 4*) showed an uncertain position in the phylogeny. It was nested in the “*somuncurae*” group based on mitochondrial markers, while it was included in the “*kingii* + *archeforus*” group based on nuclear markers. The authors attributed this discordance to past hybridization events with asymmetric mitochondrial flow. In a taxonomic review of the *lineomaculatus* section based on morphological characters and coloration patterns, Breitman et al. (2013) corroborated the findings of Breitman et al. (2011) and used the term “*kingii* group” to refer to the species included in the “*kingii* + *archeforus*” groups defined previously based on morphological characters (Scolaro and Cei 1997). The “*kingii* group” encompassed the species of the “*somuncurae* group” as well.

Subsequent studies conducted by Breitman et al. focused on unraveling the phylogeographic structure of the *kingii* group (Breitman 2013; Breitman et al. 2015b, 2015a). Breitman et al. (2015b) analyzed the northernmost members *L. somuncurae*, *L. uptoni*, and the candidate species *L. sp. 4*, using *cytb* sequences and morphometric characters. In this study, the potential evolutionary independence of *L. sp. 4* was confirmed, and two additional candidate species phylogenetically related to it were suggested. Based on a similar approach, Breitman et al. (2015a) analyzed the southernmost members of this group: *L. baguali*, *L. escarchadosi*, *L. sarmientoii*, and *L. tari*, confirming their evolutionary independence and providing support for a candidate species named *L. sp. A*.

The latest research on the *kingii* group involved comprehensive genomic data and model-based statistical approaches. Sánchez et al. (2021) analyzed the southernmost lineages, revealing ambiguous support for the current taxonomy due to the lack of divergence support between *L. escarchadosi* and *L. tari*. Additionally, this study unveiled the initial evidence of introgression within the group, particularly between *L. baguali* and *L. tari*. Building on these findings, Sánchez et al. (2023a) extended the results to the broader *kingii* clade, identifying evidence of both ancestral and recent introgression events. This work also found consistent support for the evolutionary independence of *L. sp. 4* (*L. kingii* 1 in that paper). This outcome led to the diagnosis and description of this lineage, named *L. attenboroughi* (Sánchez et al. 2023b).

Before the taxonomic proposals derived from this work, the “*kingii*” group included 14 described species distributed in two clades: 1) the *L. kingii* clade (*L. archeforus*, *L. baguali*, *L. chacabucoense*,

L. escarchadosi, *L. gallardoi*, *L. kingii*, *L. sarmientoi*, *L. scolaroi*, *L. tari*, *L. tristis*, and *L. zullyae*), and 2) The *L. somuncurae* clade (*L. attenboroughi*³, *L. somuncurae*, and *L. uptoni*).

Text S2: Taxonomic proposals

Our findings, along with recent research (Sánchez et al. 2021, 2023a), challenge the current taxonomic hypothesis of 14 species within the *kingii* group. Instead, genetic data supports the recognition of at most eight entities, while phenotypic differentiation among lineages was shown to be moderate, particularly in the geometric dataset. However, we observed concordant instances of genetic and morphometric divergences (Figs. 1 and 2 in the main text, and Figs. S6–S11). The genomic clusters partially match taxonomic treatments of the *kingii* group, including *L. attenboroughi*, *L. baguali*, and *L. chacabucoense*. The remaining groups consist of mixtures of specimens assigned to two (*somuncurae* clade and “South” group) or even three taxonomic species (“West” group). This phylogeographic structure is consistent with previous coalescent estimates of species limits (Sánchez et al. 2023a). The highly polymorphic dorsal coloration of species included in the *kingii* group may have led to the diagnosis and description of several species that do not exhibit genetic differentiation, exemplified by the case of *L. gallardoi* (Fig. 1 in the main text). This somewhat contrasts suggestions that lineages with limited dispersal (such as the lizards in this group) and strong evolutionary or developmental constraints are more likely to develop phylogeographic structure without noticeable phenotypic diversity (Bickford et al. 2007). Patterns of deep phylogeographic structure with little to no morphological variation have been observed in Patagonian lizards of the *L. rothi* complex (Olave et al. 2017) and populations of the sister genus *Phymaturus* (*P. patagonicus* clade; González Marín et al. 2018). A plausible hypothesis is that such patterns result from stabilizing selection acting on traits that characterize species (Zamudio et al. 2016). However, a comprehensive macro-evolutionary analysis of phenotypic trends incorporating representatives from all the Liolaemidae family is needed to address this hypothesis.

The populations surrounding the Somun-Curá plateau (*somuncurae* clade), taxonomically assigned to *L. somuncurae* and *L. uptoni*, did not show differentiation in any of the analyzed data. Moreover, they exhibited some degree of genetic connectivity according to effective migration estimates (Fig. 1c in the main text). Therefore, we consider them as a single evolutionary lineage.

Concerning the southern populations, we did not observe differentiation among *L. escarchadosi*, *L. tari*, and the deep mitochondrial lineage sp. A based on genomic data. Consequently, all three were grouped together in the “South” group. This lack of differentiation was partly supported by phenotypic data; however, linear data distinctly separated *L. tari* males (see Fig. S7). However, due to the unavailability of samples from its type locality, we refrain from making definitive taxonomic statements about this species. *Liolaemus sarmientoi*, although not included in our genomic dataset, was previously identified as phylogenetically nested within *L. escarchadosi* in recent studies using RADseq data (Sánchez et al. 2021, 2023a). In those studies, mitochondrial sequences of this species were consistently inferred in a well-supported clade. We posit that this observed pattern might be elucidated by the persistence of genetic traces from past events of divergence in the mitochondrion (“ghost” lineages), even when they no longer correspond to a nuclear lineage (Dufresnes et al. 2023). The morphometric data of *L. sarmientoi* analyzed here did not provide support for its distinction (see Fig. S6). Following the principles of taxonomic nomenclature [ICZN (1999); Art. 23], we use the name *L. sarmientoi* Donoso-Barros 1973 to encompass all lineages nested within the “South” group, excluding *L. tari*. Nonetheless, we hypothesize that *L. tari* is also part of this lineage.

³according to nuclear data.

The geographic distribution of this lineage is limited to the north by the Chalia and Chico fluvial systems and to the south by the Magallanes Strait, in the southern margin of Santa Cruz Province (see Fig. 1b in the main text).

Liolaemus scolaroi and *L. zullyae*, nested in the “West” group, were previously considered a single evolutionary lineage due to the absence of molecular distinctiveness (*L. scolaroi-zullyae*; Sánchez et al. 2023a). The authors of that paper also pointed to a lack of external phenotypic differences, although no formal statistic tests were conducted. Our results corroborate those suggestions (Fig. S8). The genomic data analyzed here was also unable to differentiate between *L. archeforus* and *L. scolaroi-zullyae*. Notably, the two samples of *L. scolaroi-zullyae* were collected in a transitional area between *L. archeforus* and *L. chacabucoense* (Fig. 1b in the main text). These samples exhibited a mixed genomic composition with contributions from both lineages, further indicating ongoing gene flow (Figs. 2 and 3a in the main text). We propose that *L. scolaroi* should be regarded as a junior synonym of *L. zullyae*, while the distinction between both lineages and *L. archeforus* remains to be tested after conducting more genetic sampling. The synonymy between *L. scolaroi* and *L. zullyae* has been proposed in earlier publications (Breitman et al. 2011, 2014; Demangel 2016). However, the suggestion of Demangel (2016) was disregarded due to the absence of a clear methodological framework and peer review (Troncoso-Palacios et al. 2019). *Liolaemus tristis* displayed phenotypic differentiation from *L. scolaroi* (females) and *L. zullyae* (males; Fig. S7), and previous species delimitations provided moderate to high support for its distinction from its sister species *L. archeforus* (Sánchez et al. 2023a). Based on these findings and because we were not able to collect samples from its type locality, we leave for future work to specifically test the divergence between *L. tristis* and *L. archeforus*. The species status of *L. chacabucoense* remains uncertain, as it did not show phenotypic differentiation and was nested within the “West” group, rendering it paraphyletic. Future studies should investigate the possibility that all the western populations, including *L. tristis*, represent a single evolutionary entity because of their generally lack of phenotypic differentiation. However, given the complex pathways that can take the divergence processes, this is not necessarily indicative of a lack of speciation (Pyron et al. 2023).

The recent phylogenomic study of the *kingii* clade (Sánchez et al. 2023a) revealed mitochondrial haplotypes of *L. gallardoi* and *L. sarmientoii* included in the “Deseado” clade based on nuclear data, indicating complex patterns of past hybridization accompanied by mitochondrial capture. The taxonomic status of *L. gallardoi* remains inconclusive, although phenotypically, it showed some degree of differentiation from the lineages with whom it shared genomic ancestries (Fig. S10). The type locality of *L. gallardoi* is included in a broad hybrid zone, and the genomic data indicated a high degree of admixed ancestry with contributions from *L. baguali*, the “Deseado” clade, and the “West” group (admixing area 4; Figs. 1 and 2 in the main text). This observation might explain the high polymorphism in dorsal color patterns observed in samples collected from the type locality (Fig. 1 in the main text), complicating a consistent diagnosis. Further investigation is needed to resolve the specific status of *L. gallardoi*, including the complex admixture patterns observed in the populations surrounding its type locality.

The only exception to this ubiquitous pattern of species lumping was *L. kingii*. Individuals taxonomically assigned to this species consistently exhibited differentiation into distinct northern (*kingii*) and southern populations (“Deseado” clade; Figs. 1 and 2 in the main text), a divergence also reported in Sánchez et al. (2023a). The Deseado river valley, serving as a physical barrier, separates these two groups, further reinforcing their genetic isolation (Fig. 1c in the main text). Moreover, the phenotypic differences between these groups were supported by linear and geometric data (Fig. S9). Interestingly, Cei and Scolaro (1996) highlighted variations in the average number of

scales around the midbody in *L. kingii*, with lower counts observed in populations south of the Deseado river compared to individuals of the type locality. Our data also supports this claim ($t_{343} = -3.2165$, $p = 0.001421$). A more comprehensive sampling in the transition area between these lineages will allow us to determine whether the “Deseado” clade is following an evolutionary trajectory independent from that of *L. kingii*.

Below, we summarize the taxonomic proposals derived from our results:

- *Liolaemus uptoni* Scolaro and Cei 2006 is a junior synonym of *L. somuncurae* Cei and Scolaro 1981.
- *Liolaemus escarchadosi* Scolaro and Cei 1997 is a junior synonym of *L. sarmientoi* Donoso-Barros 1973.
- *Liolaemus scolaroi* Pincheira-Donoso and Núñez 2005 is a junior synonym of *L. zullyae* Cei and Scolaro 1996.

Supplementary methods

Methods S1: Species delimitation using ibpp

To conduct species delimitation based on phenotypic data we analyzed the linear (measurements + meristic data) and geometric data separately. We focused only on male specimens. We assessed the support for speciation events in the same sub-groups defined in the PCA, in all cases we also included a closely related outgroup:

1. *gallardoi* – *baguali (outgroup: *attenboroughi*)
2. *gallardoi* – “Deseado” clade (outgroup: *attenboroughi*)
3. *gallardoi* – “West” group (*archeforus* + *scolaroi* + *zullyae*) (outgroup: *attenboroughi*)
4. *kingii* – “Deseado” clade; outgroup: *attenboroughi* (outgroup: *attenboroughi**)
5. Northern populations: *attenboroughi* – *somuncurae* – *uptoni* (outgroup: *baguali*)
6. Southern populations: *baguali* – *escarchadosi* – *sarmientoi* – *tari* – sp. A (outgroup: *attenboroughi*)
7. Western populations: *archeforus* – *chacabucoense* – *scolaroi* – *tristis* – *zullyae* (outgroup: *attenboroughi*)

In IBPP, the MCMC does not move between different tree topologies, i.e. it assess speciation events on a fixed species tree. Hence, we specified different relationships for the southern and western populations based on previous phylogenetic hypotheses (Breitman et al. 2011; Sánchez et al. 2021, 2023a):

- Southern populations:
 - ((*baguali*, (*tari*, (*spA*, (*escarchadosi*, *sarmientoi*))))), *attenboroughi*);
 - ((*baguali*, (*tari*, (*sarmientoi*, (*escarchadosi*, *spA*))))), *attenboroughi*);
 - ((*baguali*, (*spA*, (*sarmientoi*, (*escarchadosi*, *tari*))))), *attenboroughi*);
- Western populations:
 - ((*tristis*, (*chacabucoense*, (*archeforus*, (*scolaroi*, *zullyae*))))), *attenboroughi*);
 - ((*chacabucoense*, (*tristis*, (*archeforus*, (*scolaroi*, *zullyae*))))), *attenboroughi*);

Given that when analyzing all individuals in each group we encountered mixing problems in the MCMC, we conducted analyzes using two sets of six specimens from each group. For each group we conducted a PCA of the linear and geometric data of males and extracted those PCs explaining up to 90% of total variation using the `prcomp()` function in R. To check for consistency, we conducted two replicate analyzes each for two different reversible jump proposals (algorithms 0 and 1; Yang and Rannala 2010). The total number of analyzes was $10 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 = 160$:

- Five subgroups were related by a single species tree, one subgroup by three species trees and one subgroup by two species trees $\rightarrow 10$ analyzes
- Two datasets (linear and geometric) $\rightarrow 2$ analyzes
- Two random samplings in each population $\rightarrow 2$ analyzes
- Two rjMCMC algorithms $\rightarrow 2$ analyzes
- Two independent runs for each algorithm $\rightarrow 2$ analyzes

The settings of the MCMC were:

- Chain length: 100,000 sampled every 10 after a burn-in of 10,000 for the first four sub-groups.
- Chain length: 200,000 sampled every 20 after a burn-in of 20,000 for the northern populations.
- Chain length: 500,000 sampled every 50 after a burn-in of 60,000 for the southern and western populations.

In all cases we specified $\Gamma(2, 300)$ and $\Gamma(2, 1000)$ priors for the population sizes (θ) and the divergence time in the root of the species tree (τ) based on previous parameter inferences (Sánchez et al. 2023a).

Figure S11 shows the results of the species delimitation analyzes, MCMC samples of replicated analyzes were combined to estimate the posterior probability of speciation events.

Methods S2: Step-by-step approach for constructing the MSC + i model

To generate a full MSC + i model of the *kingii* group we first employed heuristic approaches implemented in PHYLONETWORKS and DELIMITR. The first method estimates introgression events between non-sister populations, and the second was used to fit models of divergence-only, isolation-with-initial-migration (IIM), and secondary contact (SC) between sister populations. The inferred events of gene flow included:

- PHYLONETWORKS:
 - Ancestral introgression from the “West” group to *Liolaemus attenboroughi*.
- DELIMITR:
 - Secondary contact between *L. baguali* and the “South” group.
 - Secondary contact between *L. chacabucoense* and the “West” group.
 - Secondary contact between *L. kingii* and the “Deseado” clade.

Second, we employed BPP to fit one introgression at a time using the `msci-create` utility, based on two individuals per specimen and 1000 loci (2000 alleles). Following parameter estimation (analysis A00), we calculated the Savage-Density ratio (Dickey 1971) between the introgression model (H_1 , i.e. $\varphi > 0$) and the null model of no introgression (H_0 ; i.e. $\varphi \approx 0$) as an approximation of the Bayes Factor (Ji et al. 2023):

$$\text{BF}_{10,\varepsilon} = \frac{\mathbb{P}(\phi)}{\mathbb{P}(\phi|\mathbf{X})} = \frac{\mathbb{P}(0 \leq X \leq \varepsilon)}{\mathbb{P}(\varphi < \varepsilon)},$$

Here, $\phi : |\varphi - \varphi_0| < \varepsilon$ is a region of negligible gene flow in H_1 representing H_0 . In this formula, the

numerator is defined by the cumulative density function (CDF) for the prior on the introgression probability and the denominator is the proportion of φ values sampled during the MCMC simulation that are $< \varepsilon$ (see Figure 2 in Ji et al. 2023). In BPP, the prior on the introgression probability is usually assigned a prior $B(1, 1) = U(0, 1)$, hence the numerator $\mathbb{P}(\phi) = \varepsilon$. For consistency, we specified different values of ε (0.05, 0.005, and 0.0005) and considered introgression events with $BF_{10,\varepsilon} > 20$, which is analogous to a frequentist 5% “significance level”. It worths to bear in mind that Bayesian model selection may strongly support the null model, unlike the likelihood ratio test which fails to reject the null model but never strongly supports it (Flouri et al. 2023).

The advantage of approximating the Bayes Factor through the Savage-Dickey density ratio is that only requires parameter estimation under the H_1 model, which reduces the amount of computation. It applies to Bayesian testing of nested hypothesis; however, it could be used to compare nonnested models as long as they have the same null model as a special case.

The time of introgression between the “West” group and *L. attenboroughi* was very close to the divergence time between the “West” group and *L. chacabucoense*. If an introgression event is mis-specified, i.e. assigned incorrectly to a daughter branch to the lineage truly involved in introgression, the estimated introgression time would collapse onto the species divergence time (Ji et al. 2023; Thawornwattana et al. 2023). Because of that we also inferred the timing and amount of introgression between *L. attenboroughi* and each, *L. chacabucoense* and the ancestor of clade “West” group + *L. chacabucoense*. Also, for each introgression event we calculated the S-D density ratio of the model in the opposite direction.

Table S5 shows the introgression models and the Bayes Factor comparison between each model and the null model of no gene flow. Only introgression events with $BF_{10,\varepsilon} > 20$ for the three values of ε and whose time did not overlap the divergence time of the lineages involved were considered for the next stage

In the third stage we added introgression events sequentially in the order of decreasing strength of φ . At each step, the added introgression event was retained if it met the same cutoff defined above. To ensure proper mixing, we reduced the data size to 500 loci (1000 alleles). The results of this stage are shown in Table S6.

Finally, we constructed a full MSC + i model including all the supported introgression events using 2000 alleles. This MSC + i model was time-calibrated using per-generation substitution rates, following Sánchez et al. (2023a) (details in the R script `phylogeography.R`).

Supplementary tables

Table S1. Normal mixture modeling (GFMM) of taxonomic hypotheses and model classification according to the Bayesian information criterion (BIC). Values in parentheses are Δ BIC of each model against the current taxonomic hypothesis (shown with an asterisk). The top ranked models for each comparison are shown in bold.

Sub-group	Taxonomic species	N	linear σ	linear ϱ	geometric σ
Northern populations	<i>att.</i> / <i>som.</i> / <i>upt.</i> *	3	149.28 (-)	221.73 (-)	346.74 (-)
	<i>att.</i> / (<i>som.</i> + <i>upt.</i>)	2	160.5 (11.22)	232.34 (10.61)	363.99 (17.25)
	(<i>att.</i> + <i>som.</i> + <i>upt.</i>)	1	172.11 (23.83)	243.18 (21.45)	373.03 (26.29)
Southern populations	<i>bag.</i> / <i>esc.</i> / <i>sar.</i> / <i>tar.</i> / sp. A	5	83.26 (-24.09)	492.27 (-28.24)	1302.96 (-19.03)
	<i>bag.</i> / (<i>esc.</i> + sp. A) / <i>sar.</i> / <i>tar.</i> *	4	107.35 (-)	520.51 (-)	1321.99 (-)
	<i>bag.</i> / (<i>esc.</i> + <i>sar.</i> + sp. A) / <i>tar.</i>	3	121.82 (14.47)	596.03 (75.52)	1338.19 (16.2)
	<i>bag.</i> / (<i>esc.</i> + <i>tar.</i> + sp. A) / <i>sar.</i>	3	144.59 (37.24)	567.88 (47.37)	1338.78 (16.79)
	<i>bag.</i> / (<i>esc.</i> + <i>sar.</i> + <i>tar.</i> + sp. A)	2	158.77 (51.42)	643.87 (123.36)	1354.25 (32.26)
	(<i>bag.</i> + <i>esc.</i> + <i>sar.</i> + <i>tar.</i> + sp. A)	1	157.98 (50.63)	681.53 (161.02)	1374.78 (52.79)
Western populations	<i>arc.</i> / <i>cha.</i> / <i>sco.</i> / <i>tri.</i> / <i>zul.</i> *	5	850.97 (-)	4.04 (-)	2211.89 (-)
	<i>arc.</i> / <i>cha.</i> / (<i>sco.</i> + <i>zul.</i>) / <i>tri.</i>	4	921.69 (70.72)	18.57 (14.53)	2223.23 (11.34)
	(<i>arc.</i> + <i>sco.</i> + <i>zul.</i>) / <i>cha.</i> / <i>tri.</i>	3	988.49 (137.52)	30.74 (26.7)	2230.85 (11.96)
	(<i>arc.</i> + <i>tri.</i>) / <i>cha.</i> / (<i>sco.</i> + <i>zul.</i>)	3	983.99 (133.02)	29.76 (25.72)	2240.15 (28.26)
	(<i>arc.</i> + <i>sco.</i> + <i>tri.</i> + <i>zul.</i>) / <i>cha.</i>	2	1049.09 (198.12)	42.38 (38.34)	2241.11 (29.22)
	(<i>arc.</i> + <i>cha.</i> + <i>sco.</i> + <i>zul.</i>) / <i>tri.</i>	2	1048.25 (197.28)	39.46 (35.42)	2249.36 (37.47)
	(<i>arc.</i> + <i>cha.</i> + <i>sco.</i> + <i>tri.</i> + <i>zul.</i>)	1	1113.87 (262.9)	53.9 (49.86)	2260.17 (48.28)
<i>kingii</i> vs. “Deseado clade”	<i>kin.</i> / “Des”.	2	7159.52 (-152.82)	3550.19 (-106.5)	19427.67 (-68.61)
	(<i>kin.</i> + “Des”.)*	1	7312.34 (-)	3656.69 (-)	19496.28 (-)
<i>baguali</i>	<i>gal.</i> / <i>bag.</i> *	2	97.86 (-)	179.57 (-)	638.94 (-)
	(<i>gal.</i> + <i>bag.</i>)	1	122.4 (24.54)	192.1 (12.53)	653.67 (14.73)
<i>gallardoi</i> vs. “Deseado” clade	<i>gal.</i> / “Des”*	2	908.27 (-)	1755.94 (-)	7425.95 (-)
	(<i>gal.</i> + “Des”.)	1	953.06 (44.79)	1834.84 (78.9)	7476.01 (50.06)
West group	<i>gal.</i> / Wes.*	2	361.81 (-)	129.88 (-)	2205.44 (-)
	(<i>gal.</i> + Wes.)	1	378.8 (16.99)	167.2 (37.32)	2239.55 (34.11)

Table S2. Results of statistical tests of the relationship between spatial and climatic variables and genetic distances.

Variable	DF	Variance	F	$P(>F)$
Geographic distances	13	7.5915	1.4018	0.001
Vegetation (PC)	1	0.5558	1.3343	0.012
Elevation	1	0.5228	1.255	0.022
Curr. clim. (PC)	1	0.4804	1.1531	0.088
LGM (PC)	1	0.4547	1.0914	0.179
LIG (PC)	1	0.4554	1.0931	0.182
MIS19 (PC)	1	0.5017	1.2043	0.058
mPWP (PC)	1	0.5322	1.2775	0.019
M2 (PC)	1	0.5717	1.2043	0.004
Residual	66	27.4951		

Table S3. Results of statistical tests of the relationship between spatial and climatic variables and genetic distances for *L. kingii* and the “Deseado” clade.

Variable	DF	Variance	<i>F</i>	<i>P</i> (> <i>F</i>)
Geographic distances	2	2.553	1.0934	0.044
Vegetation (PC)	1	1.101	0.9434	0.913
Elevation	1	1.13	0.9676	0.728
Curr. clim. (PC)	1	1.133	0.9702	0.67
LGM (PC)	1	1.136	0.9729	0.636
LIG (PC)	1	1.135	0.9725	0.657
Residual	36	42.031		

Table S4. Comparison between tree and network models to explain phenotypic attributes. ΔAICc shows the difference in the AICc score between the tree (null model) and the network.

Dataset	Variable	tree (logLik)	network (logLik)	tree (AICc)	network (AICc)	ΔAICc
Linear full	SVL	1185.82	1185.91	-2365.6	-2365.79	0.185147
	AL	1423.73	1424.04	-2841.43	-2842.04	0.60603
	TFL	1361.48	1361.73	-2716.93	-2717.43	0.499803
	HH	1223.31	1223.17	-2440.58	-2440.31	-0.271314
	HW	1203.49	1203.78	-2400.95	-2401.53	0.5812
	RND	1258.31	1258.51	-2510.59	-2510.98	0.391784
Linear σ	SVL	592.135	592.349	-1178.19	-1178.62	0.427692
	AL	675.794	676.126	-1345.51	-1346.18	0.664254
	TFL	651.653	651.877	-1297.23	-1297.68	0.448084
	HH	604.521	604.726	-1202.97	-1203.38	0.411191
	HW	595.315	595.628	-1184.56	-1185.18	0.625009
	RND	620.401	620.747	-1234.73	-1235.42	0.691886
Linear φ	SVL	629.86	629.917	-1253.65	-1253.76	0.112915
	AL	792.669	792.976	-1579.27	-1579.88	0.61281
	TFL	778.516	778.78	-1550.96	-1551.49	0.528159
	HH	670.008	670.223	-1333.95	-1334.38	0.429839
	HW	708.461	708.793	-1410.85	-1411.52	0.664432
	RND	669.676	670.025	-1333.28	-1333.98	0.698136
Geometric σ	PC1	730.32	730.318	-1454.56	-1454.56	-0.00373836
	PC2	785.497	785.634	-1564.92	-1565.19	0.273264
	PC3	816.85	817.012	-1627.62	-1627.94	0.323761
	PC4	864.599	864.788	-1723.12	-1723.5	0.379476
	PC5	907.629	907.626	-1809.18	-1809.17	-0.00640991
	PC6	929.205	929.178	-1852.33	-1852.28	-0.0538512
	PC7	1000.84	1000.67	-1995.6	-1995.26	-0.34018
	PC8	1017.01	1017.12	-2027.93	-2028.16	0.225321
	PC9	1041.92	1041.88	-2077.76	-2077.67	-0.0869203
	PC10	1071.03	1071.28	-2135.98	-2136.48	0.501659
	PC11	1082.54	1082.53	-2159.01	-2158.99	-0.0218183

Table S5. BPP estimates of posterior means and 95% HPD CIs of φ for each of the introgression events suggested by PHYLONETWORKS and DELIMITR. We also show the Bayes Factor comparison between each introgression model and the null model of no gene flow (given by the Savage-Dickey density ratio).

Inferred in	Introgression	Mean φ (95% HPD CI)	Introgression time near divergence node?	BF ₁₀ ($\varepsilon = 0.0005$)	BF ₁₀ ($\varepsilon = 0.005$)	BF ₁₀ ($\varepsilon = 0.05$)	Next stage (Table S6)
PHYLONETWORKS*	<i>att.</i> → (“Wes.” + <i>cha.</i>)	0.083 (0.053 – 0.116)	no	∞	∞	5.435	no
PHYLONETWORKS*	(“Wes.” + <i>cha.</i>) → <i>att.</i>	0.492 (0.408 – 0.571)	no	∞	∞	∞	yes
PHYLONETWORKS*	<i>att.</i> → <i>cha.</i>	0.06 (0.029 – 0.089)	yes	∞	∞	0.179	no
PHYLONETWORKS*	<i>cha.</i> → <i>att.</i>	0.348 (0.267 – 0.43)	no	∞	∞	∞	yes
PHYLONETWORKS*	<i>att.</i> → “Wes.”	0.036 (0.018 – 0.057)	yes	∞	50	0.055	no
PHYLONETWORKS	“Wes.” → <i>att.</i>	0.352 (0.271 – 0.43)	yes	∞	∞	∞	yes
DELIMITR (<i>bag.</i> ↔ “Sou.”)	<i>bag.</i> → “Sou.”	0.063 (0.001 – 0.128)	no	2.273	0.577	0.123	no
DELIMITR (<i>bag.</i> ↔ “Sou.”)	“Sou.” → <i>bag.</i>	0.804 (0.687 – 0.915)	no	∞	∞	∞	yes
DELIMITR (<i>cha.</i> ↔ “Wes.”)	<i>cha.</i> → “Wes.”	0.215 (0.018 – 0.555)	no	2	5.495	1.136	no
DELIMITR (<i>cha.</i> ↔ “Wes.”)	“Wes.” → <i>cha.</i>	0.826 (0.586 – 1)	no	∞	∞	∞	yes
DELIMITR (<i>kin.</i> ↔ “Des.”)	<i>kin.</i> → “Des.”	0.168 (0.079 – 0.268)	no	∞	∞	166.667	yes
DELIMITR (<i>kin.</i> ↔ “Des.”)	“Des.” → <i>kin.</i>	0.856 (0.777 – 0.929)	no	∞	∞	∞	yes

* The only introgression event suggested by PHYLONETWORKS was “Wes.” → *att.*, however we assessed alternative placements and directions of the hybrid branch (see Methods S2).

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Table S6. Introgression models supported in the previous step ordered according to their mean introgression probabilities (Table S5). We added each event sequentially and calculated the Bayes factor. Those that showed significant support (BF > 20) were included in the full MSC + i model of the group.

Ranking (mean φ)	Model	BF ₁₀ ($\varepsilon = 0.0005$)	BF ₁₀ ($\varepsilon = 0.005$)	BF ₁₀ ($\varepsilon = 0.05$)	Included in full model
1*	“Des.” → <i>kin.</i>	0.789	0.564	0.485	no
2*	<i>kin.</i> → “Des.”	0.214	0.305	0.362	no
3	“Wes.” → <i>cha.</i>	5	1.714	1.862	no
4	“Sou.” → <i>bag.</i>	∞	66.667	25.974	yes
5	(“Wes.” + <i>cha.</i>) → <i>att.</i>	∞	∞	∞	yes
6	<i>cha.</i> → <i>att.</i>	0.04	0.041	0.062	no

* These introgression events were merged in a single bidirectional model.

Supplementary figures

Figure S1. Location of landmarks (red dots) and semi-landmarks (blue dots) used to describe the head shape. Taken from Sánchez et al. (2021).

Figure S2. Cross-validation results for different numbers of ancestral populations (K) estimated in TESS3R.

Figure S3. Cross-entropy results for different numbers of ancestral populations (K) estimated in LEA.

Figure S4. AIC results for different numbers of ancestral populations (K) estimated in SNAPCLUST.

Figure S5. Posterior mean diversity rates (q) showing areas of lower (brown) and higher (blue) diversity rates than expected under IBD.

Figure S6. Bi-plots of principal components and statistical significance of multivariate analysis of morphological variation (PERMANOVA). Comparisons between *L. attenboroughi* and species included in the *somuncurae* clade (*L. somuncurae* and *L. uptoni*). The values in the boxes correspond to the R^2 statistic: the proportion of total variance in the multivariate data that is explained by the grouping factor (species). Statistically significant differences, as given by the pseudo-F test statistic, are indicated with grey boxes, and the asterisks denote cutpoints of adjusted p -values: “***” 0.001, “**” 0.001–0.01, “*” 0.01–0.05. The boxes show the shape variations across PC space of the geometric data (red dots: landmarks, blue dots: semi-landmarks); this was obtained with the `plotRefToTarget()` of the package GEOMORPH comparing the minimum value (reference) and the maximum value (target) for each axis.

Figure S7. Bi-plots of principal components and statistical significance of multivariate analysis of morphological variation (PERMANOVA). Comparisons between species included in the southern populations. The values in the boxes correspond to the R^2 statistic: the proportion of total variance in the multivariate data that is explained by the grouping factor (species). Statistically significant differences, as given by the pseudo-F test statistic, are indicated with grey boxes, and the asterisks denote cutpoints of adjusted p -values: “***” ≤ 0.001 , “**” 0.001–0.01, “*” 0.01–0.05. The boxes show the shape variations across PC space of the geometric data (red dots: landmarks, blue dots: semi-landmarks); this was obtained with the `plotRefToTarget()` of the package `GEOMORPH` comparing the minimum value (reference) and the maximum value (target) for each axis.

Figure S8. Bi-plots of principal components and statistical significance of multivariate analysis of morphological variation (PERMANOVA). Comparisons between species included in the western populations. The values in the boxes correspond to the R^2 statistic: the proportion of total variance in the multivariate data that is explained by the grouping factor (species). Statistically significant differences, as given by the pseudo-F test statistic, are indicated with grey boxes, and the asterisks denote cutpoints of adjusted p -values: “” ≤ 0.001 , “” $0.001-0.01$, “” $0.01-0.05$. The boxes show the shape variations across PC space of the geometric data (red dots: landmarks, blue dots: semi-landmarks); this was obtained with the `plotRefToTarget()` of the package GEOMORPH comparing the minimum value (reference) and the maximum value (target) for each axis.

Figure S9. Bi-plots of principal components and statistical significance of multivariate analysis of morphological variation (PERMANOVA). Comparisons between *L. kingii* and the “Deseado” clade. The values in the boxes correspond to the R^2 statistic: the proportion of total variance in the multivariate data that is explained by the grouping factor (species). Statistically significant differences, as given by the pseudo-F test statistic, are indicated with grey boxes, and the asterisks denote cutpoints of adjusted p -values: “***” ≤ 0.001 , “**” 0.001–0.01, “*” 0.01–0.05. The boxes show the shape variations across PC space of the geometric data (red dots: landmarks, blue dots: semi-landmarks); this was obtained with the `plotRefToTarget()` of the package GEOMORPH comparing the minimum value (reference) and the maximum value (target) for each axis.

Figure S10. Bi-plots of principal components and statistical significance of multivariate analysis of morphological variation (PERMANOVA). Comparisons between *L. gallardoi*, *L. baguali*, the “Deseado” clade, and the “West” group. The values in the boxes correspond to the R^2 statistic: the proportion of total variance in the multivariate data that is explained by the grouping factor (species). Statistically significant differences, as given by the pseudo-F test statistic, are indicated with grey boxes, and the asterisks denote cutpoints of adjusted p -values: “***” ≤ 0.001 , “**” 0.001–0.01, “*” 0.01–0.05. The boxes show the shape variations across PC space of the geometric data (red dots: landmarks, blue dots: semi-landmarks); this was obtained with the `plotRefToTarget()` of the package GEOMORPH comparing the minimum value (reference) and the maximum value (target) for each axis.

Figure S11. Summary of posterior probabilities of speciation events based on phenotypic data according to IBPP. Results are shown for each subgroup based on linear (measurements + meristic) and geometric data. Two samples were drawn for each lineage (samples 1 and 2), and two replicate runs were performed for rjMCMC algorithms 0 and 1. Also are shown the prior densities for the population sizes (θ) and divergence time on the root of the species tree (τ_0)

Figure S12. Left: Phylogenomic network with branch lengths representing coalescent units. Right: Phylogenomic network with time-consistent branch lengths (ultrametric). Both networks correspond to the optimal configuration suggested by broken-stick heuristics of pseudo-likelihood values.

Figure S13. Performance of real and randomly shuffled dependent variables to predict the genetic differentiation between *L. kingii* and the "Deseado" clade.

Figure S14. Predicted areas for members of the northern populations (*Liolaemus attenboroughi* and the *somuncurae* clade), across different time windows.

Figure S15. Predicted areas for members of the southern populations (*Liolaemus baguali* and “South” group), including their ancestral populations, across different time windows.

Figure S16. Predicted areas for members of the western populations (*Liolaemus chacabucoense* and "West" group), including their ancestral populations, across different time windows.

Figure S17. Predicted areas of *Liolaemus kingii* and the “Deseado” clade, including their ancestral populations, across different time windows.

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